

Perinatal Outcome in Cases with Bleeding During First and Early Second Trimester

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Abstract : A. Background Bleeding during first half of pregnancy mostly originates from placenta, some abort, others are at risk of complications. B. Objective Study was done to know perinatal outcome with bleeding upto 20 weeks in singleton pregnancy. C. Material Methods Subjects were 1020, equal controls, managed over 2 years, 435 had viable pregnancy at admission, 135 excluded, 300 followed for perinatal outcome, 99 (19.52% upto 10 weeks), 201 (39.18% of 11-20 weeks). D. Results Hypertensive disorders occurred in 24% cases of bleeding within 10 weeks, 22% 11-20 weeks 14.79% controls, placenta previa 4% in 10 weeks, 0.9% 11-20 weeks, 0.97% controls, prelabor rupture of membranes in 16%, 7.45% controls. 20% upto 10 weeks, 35% 11-20 weeks, 18% controls had fetal growth restriction, 34.34% upto 10 weeks 30.35% of 11-20 weeks 17.17% controls had preterm births, perinatal mortality rate in study was 118.62, in controls 68.16 (Uneventful pregnancy in 13.52% study, 46.11% controls). E. Conclusion Once bleeding occurs, one third continue pregnancy, maternal neonatal outcome affected with are variations in bleeding within first 10 weeks & beyond.

Keywords : Bleeding, Disorders, First Second trimester, Perinatal Outcome

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